

SCIENTIFIC, SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL INTERPRETATIONS OF THE CONCEPT OF READING

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Annotation: This article analyzes the scientific, social, and philosophical interpretations of the concept of reading. The role of reading culture in the consciousness, spiritual and moral values of young people and the development of society is highlighted. The article discusses the stages of historical formation of books, reading culture, writing and reading, and their impact on human spirituality and thinking. Also, the ancient attitude of the people of Uzbekistan to books, the views of great thinkers on reading books, and the development of reading in modern society will be considered. The study substantiates that reading culture is an important factor in human socialization, thinking, and spiritual development.

Keywords: reading, culture, spirituality, philosophy, educational culture, youth, values.

In the modern world, the problem of reading culture is relevant and controversial, requiring a separate, objective approach to this issue. There is a need to substantiate and substantially supplement the concept of reading culture, to study its influence on the consciousness and spiritual and moral values of young people, to combine the results of research conducted by scientists in this area, and to study it from a scientific point of view.

It should be noted that the concept of reading culture consists of several components that make up its multifaceted integrity. These include culture, the emergence and history of books (book culture), reading, reading literacy, writing, and the reader's literacy culture. The study of these components contributes to a deep and thorough study of the phenomenon of reading culture.

Every society has its own unique cultural objects and unique cultural personalities. From the connection of these different poles, specific historical types of cultures arose. Human culture in society is very important, it is the biological personality that forms and transforms into a social personality, and at the same time regulates and educates its behavior. According to cultural scholars, "Every culture is a unique world created by a person's specific attitude towards the world and themselves. By studying different cultures, we not only study books, temples, or archaeological finds, but also discover

other human worlds where people lived and felt differently from us. Every culture is a way of creative self-awareness of a person. Therefore, understanding other cultures enriches us not only with new knowledge, but also with new creative experience."

The culture of reading (the culture of reading textual information) is the initial and main factor in the formation of the entire culture. According to expert Yu. Melentyeva, one of the components of reading culture is book culture" (Book culture, reading culture, the history of the emergence and development of books, writing is an integral part of the phenomenon of reading culture, and the book is the most complete and colorful expression of the culture of all mankind.

Reading plays an important role in the formation of spirituality and enlightenment by people. From ancient times, even before the invention of books, our ancestors told fairy tales, riddles, proverbs, and songs, even if they were original, in order to raise their children to be intelligent, resourceful, and quick-witted. In the 4th-3rd millennia BC, scrolls made from papyrus plants accelerated the promotion of culture and enlightenment. Later, in Egypt, Rome, Greece, China, and Central Asia, people wrote and expressed their thoughts on stone, palm, bamboo leaves, pottery, leather, wood, and other materials.

It is known that in Central Asia, in the 1st millennium BC, the Zoroastrian book "Avesta" was written on 12,000 cattle hides. In the 10th-11th centuries, there were libraries in Central Asia where rare books were kept. Another unique book made of leather is the Mushafi Uthman Quran. This book was written in Kufic script in 644-656 by Muhammad's (peace be upon him) scribes Zayd ibn Thabit, Amir ibn al-'As, and Hisham ibn Hakim under the direction of Caliph Uthman. This shows that the need and attention to books has been formed and developed since ancient times.

Until now, people around the world, including the Uzbek people, have understood the world through books. The fact that Umarshaykh Mirza read "Shahnameh" in "Baburnama" or Atabek read "Baburnama" in "Days Gone By" and similar notes indicate that reading has been an integral part of our spiritual values. The dastans of oral folk art "Kuntugmish," "Shirin and Shakar," "Malikai Ayyor," "Alpomish," "Gorogli" were read in families in turn. During the long winter months, storytellers enthusiastically recounted examples of folk oral art in places where people gathered. There were discussions and debates about books such as "The Story of Ibrahim Adham" and "The Story of Shah Mashrab." Of course, a legitimate question arises: why is it not so now?

In all his speeches, the head of our state pays special attention to protecting young people from harmful online attacks, teaching them to effectively use information technologies, and emphasizes the need to establish regular family libraries and develop

a culture of reading in every family. Because the level of reading is a sign of the cultural level of the family, it is necessary to organize family libraries in each family and support their educational activities in promoting family reading. "We talk a lot about changing people's consciousness and thinking," the head of our country emphasizes, "change their worldview, raise their spiritual level." But isn't a book the simplest and most effective tool in this regard? I am convinced that progress and high spirituality cannot be achieved without books. Neither a person who doesn't read books, nor a nation has a future." From the above clear idea, it can be understood that in the development of culture, the culture of books and reading guides the socialization of a person, ensures his freedom, and sharpens his thinking. Most importantly, the book contributes to the formation of healthy economic and spiritual-cultural needs in a person, directing them to a truly intellectual and moral space.

Our great thinkers understand the culture of reading as an integral part of the general culture of man. For this reason, those who evaluated the concept of reading culture from the point of view of social philosophy, which is a science that studies nature, society, thinking, and the place of man in this society, cited their valuable thoughts, and our great ancestor Az-Zamakhshari, emphasizing the importance of reading in acquiring knowledge, writes: "Knowledge is not by writing and drawing on paper, but by reading and understanding."

As F. Bacon said, "Read not to contradict and deny, not to blindly believe, not to find words for conversation, but to think and reflect."

Indeed, books are a force that encourages all of us towards goodness and helps solve all the problems before us. It is not without reason that in our country, those who are familiar with books, who love books, who write books, who consider books sacred and protect them like the apple of their eye are called intellectuals. Intellectuals are radiators of light, they are those who illuminate society with their actions and activities, ensuring spiritual and social stability.

With the formation and development of reading culture, values change as a person's general culture, morality, people's spirituality, their relationships with each other and the environment, and society itself develops.

The rapid development of electronic technologies and electronizing values, the interactive network space, has led to an increase in the number of electronic publications, the emergence of digital libraries, virtual book clubs, online communities, and numerous websites. As a result, the reader's attitude towards traditional books has changed. This, of course, does not mean that humanity has stopped learning. The Internet offers unparalleled opportunities for the development of reading. For example, if we approach this issue from a pedagogical point of view: if the teacher has mastered

information technologies well, he can organize online readers' conferences with a specific time, and invite the author of the work to this conference. Naturally, the opportunity to talk with the author about the work and ask them questions of interest will not leave young people indifferent. Organizing various reviews - contests, competitions, quizzes among readers of various institutions through the Internet, encouraging their active participants, and regularly establishing positive and creative work will give a powerful impetus to the rise of reading culture. In this regard, the head of our state expresses the following opinion: "At the same time, along with mastering the latest achievements in the field of information and communication, it is necessary to pay special attention to increasing young people's interest in reading books, making them friends with books, and further raising the reading level of the population. For this, it is important, first of all, to place the best examples of our national and world literature on social networks and pay special attention to their wide promotion."

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